

Notes

Effect of Ring Size Due to Secondary Ligand on the Stability of Some Ternary Lanthanide Complexes

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It was observed^{1,2} that in mixed ligand complexes of the type (M-bipy-L) the effect of ring size on the stability of the mixed complexes is the same as in binary complexes. It was also pointed out^{3,4} that the stability of mixed ligand complexes is affected by the size of the chelate ring and that in mixed ligand complexes containing two chelate rings the stability sequence is one five membered ring and one six membered ring > two six membered rings > two five membered rings.

The present work describes the effect of the size of ring formed by the secondary ligand on the stability of the ternary mixed ligand complex of the type LN-EDTA-L, where LN=La³⁺, Ce³⁺, Pr³⁺, Nd³⁺, Sm³⁺, EDTA=A=primary ligand and L=secondary ligand (malonate, succinate or glutarate).

The combination of lanthanides in the complexes of which the l.f.s.e. is very low and the saturated dicarboxylic acids, which form symmetrical rings, is considered appropriate for studying the effect of ring size on the stability of the mixed complexes. A pair of isomeric alanines (α and β) has also been used where the α -isomer forms a five membered ring and the β -isomer a six membered ring.

Experimental

Irving-Rossotti⁵ pH-titration technique as extended to ternary systems⁶ was applied to determine the stability constants of the complexes in aqueous medium at an ionic strength of 0.2 M NaClO₄ and at 25°. The titrations were done against 0.2 M sodium hydroxide (carbonate free). The pH values were noted using an Elico digital, LI-120 pH meter. Reproducible pH data were used for calculations.

Results and Discussion

The proton-ligand stability constants ($\log K_1^H$) of the ligands are given in Table 1. Table 2 incorporates the metal-ligand stability constants of 1:1 binary ($\log K_{ML}^M$ or $\log K_{ML}^M$) and 1:1:1 ternary ($\log K_{MAL}^M$) complexes, along with their values of ΔG , the free energy change corresponding to the ternary systems, $\Delta \log K (= \log K_{MAL}^M - \log K_{ML}^M)$ and the statistical stability constants ($\log K_s$) of the ternary complexes.

TABLE 1—PROTON-LIGAND STABILITY CONSTANTS OF THE SECONDARY LIGANDS

Ligands	I = 0.2 M, NaClO ₄ Temp. = 25°		
	$\log K_1^H$	$\log K_2^H$	$\log \beta_n^H$
Malonic acid	5.05	2.80	7.85
Succinic acid	5.24	4.10	9.34
Glutaric acid	5.45	4.22	9.67
α -Alanine	9.89	2.71	12.60
β -Alanine	9.51	3.50	13.01

The ternary systems under study are of the type $M+A \rightleftharpoons MA$; $MA+L \rightleftharpoons MAL$, where the secondary ligand L combines with MA to form the ternary complex. The much stronger complexing nature of EDTA eliminates the possibility of any ligand displacement of the type $MA+L \rightleftharpoons ML+A$. The formation of ternary complexes has also been confirmed by the non-superimposable nature of the theoretical composite curve⁷ on the experimental mixed complex curve. Formation of protonated or polynuclear species may be ignored in view of the use of very dilute solutions ($10^{-3}M$). The plots of $\bar{n}/[L]$ vs $[L]$ have been found to be smooth, indicating the absence of such species.

The formation of ternary complexes in case of dicarboxylic acids is observed to take place at relatively lower pH values where the formation of the hydroxo species may be ruled out. But in case of α - and β -alanines the formation of ternary complex takes place at higher pH range where MA gets hydrolysed. Hydrolysis correction⁸ has been applied to get the corrected values of $\log K_{MAL}^M$ in these cases. The hydrolysis corrected values are given in parenthesis along with the $\log K_{MAL}^M$ values in Table 2.

A perusal of the values of stability constants from Table 2 shows that the order of stability with respect to metal ions is La³⁺ < Ce³⁺ < Pr³⁺ < Nd³⁺ < Sm³⁺, which is the order of increasing occupancy of the 4f-orbitals of these metal ions.

The general stability sequence with respect to the secondary ligands has been observed to be malonic > succinic > glutaric. This order of stability can be explained on the basis of the size of chelate ring formed by the secondary ligand, which is malonate: 6-membered > succinate: 7-membered > glutarate: 8-membered. The greater stability of malonates may be attributed to the greater attraction associated with the larger OOC-C-COO bond angles in chelate ring with lanthanide ions⁹. The values for two isomeric alanines show that α -alanine forms more stable chelates than the β -isomer, because the former forms a five membered chelate ring whereas the latter gives a six membered chelate ring with a greater strain¹⁰.

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TABLE 2—METAL-LIGAND STABILITY CONSTANTS OF 1 : 1 BINARY AND 1 : 1 : 1 TERNARY COMPLEXES AND ΔG , $\Delta \log K$ AND $\log K_s$ VALUES

Ligand	System	Temp. -25°				
		Stability constants*				
		La ³⁺	Ce ³⁺	Pr ³⁺	Nd ³⁺	Sm ³⁺
EDTA	MA	11.53	11.83	12.15	12.53	12.83
	ML	3.80	4.11	4.26	4.50	4.87
	MAL	2.96	3.28	3.43	3.60	3.70
	- ΔG (kcal mole ⁻¹)	4.10	4.45	4.75	4.99	5.13
	- $\Delta \log K$	0.84	0.83	0.82	0.90	1.17
Malonic acid	log K _s	9.60	9.89	10.18	10.53	10.86
	ML	3.73	3.86	4.11	4.37	4.49
	MAL	3.50	3.61	3.76	3.87	4.01
	- ΔG (kcal mole ⁻¹)	4.85	5.00	5.19	5.36	5.56
	- $\Delta \log K$	0.23	0.25	0.35	0.50	0.48
Succinic acid	log K _s	9.58	9.84	10.14	10.49	10.76
	ML	3.70	3.81	4.02	4.05	4.20
	MAL	2.86	3.08	3.22	3.37	3.51
	- ΔG (kcal mole ⁻¹)	3.96	4.26	4.46	4.67	4.86
	- $\Delta \log K$	0.84	0.74	0.80	0.68	0.75
Glutaric acid	log K _s	9.58	9.82	10.12	10.41	10.71
	ML	5.82	6.03	6.36	6.52	6.88
	MAL	4.28	4.40	4.99	5.17	5.37
	- ΔG (kcal mole ⁻¹)	(4.00)	(4.39)	(4.41)	(4.96)	(-)
	- $\Delta \log K$	5.87	6.04	6.85	7.09	7.38
α -Alanine	log K _s	1.54	1.63	1.37	1.35	1.31
	ML	10.10	10.38	10.70	11.03	11.31
	MAL	5.20	5.90	6.08	6.24	6.40
	- ΔG (kcal mole ⁻¹)	4.33	4.37	4.49	4.72	4.99
	- $\Delta \log K$	(4.20)	(4.30)	(4.41)	(4.62)	(4.86)
β -Alanine	log K _s	6.00	6.06	6.22	6.54	6.92
	ML	0.87	1.53	1.59	1.52	1.41
	MAL	9.98	10.34	10.63	10.96	11.23
	- ΔG (kcal mole ⁻¹)					
	- $\Delta \log K$					

*Corrected values in parenthesis.

The general order of stability for the complexes has been found to be $\log K_{ML}^M \gg \log K_{ML}^M > \log K_{MAL}^{MAL}$. The values of $\log K_{ML}^M$ greater than $\log K_{MAL}^{MAL}$ may be due to coulombic repulsion between (LN-EDTA)⁻ species and L³⁺ or L²⁺. The steric repulsions are also expected to lower the stability of the ternary complexes¹¹.

The statistical stability constants ($\log K_s$) have also been calculated¹² assuming lanthanide metal ions to be octacoordinated, primary ligand as hexadentate and secondary ligand as bidentate. The $\log K_s$ values are found to be greater than the experimental values of $\log K_{MAL}^{MAL}$. This indicates the involvement of astatistical factors in the formation of mixed complexes.

The $-\Delta \log K$ values lie in the range 0.23 to 1.17 in the case of dicarboxylic acids, and 0.87 to 1.63 for α - and β -alanines. The effect of ring size on the stability constants of the ternary complexes can be examined by calculating $\Delta \Delta \log K$ values where,

$$\Delta \Delta \log K = \Delta \log K_{large\ ring} - \Delta \log K_{small\ ring}$$

The large sized ring is of glutaric or succinic acid whereas the small sized ring may be regarded as that for malonic acid. The calculated values of $\Delta \Delta \log K$ have been recorded in Table 3.

Positive and significant values of $\Delta \Delta \log K$ are found for the systems LN-EDTA-(glut/maln) and

LN-EDTA-(suc'maln). In the case of succinates and glutarates the negative charge is distributed over a larger moiety than in the case of malonates and this may result in the positive values of $\Delta \Delta \log K$.

TABLE 3— $\Delta \Delta \log K$ VALUES IN THE TERNARY COMPLEXES

Systems	$\Delta \Delta \log K$				
	La ³⁺	Ce ³⁺	Pr ³⁺	Nd ³⁺	Sm ³⁺
LN-EDTA-(Glu/Maln)	0.0	+0.09	+0.03	+0.21	+0.42
LN-EDTA-(Suc/Maln)	+0.61	+0.58	+0.47	+0.39	+0.69
LN-EDTA-(Glu/Suc)	-0.61	-0.49	-0.44	-0.18	-0.27

Unlike the 3d-elements the lanthanides are electropositive with large ionic radii and their 4fⁿ electrons are well shielded by the outer 5s and 5p orbitals from ligand perturbations. The metal-ligand bond should, therefore, be ionic with a minimal covalent contribution. The validity of Born relation¹³ $E = Z^2/2r(1-1/D)$ [where, E=energy of complexation, Z=charge and r=radius of metal ion] has been tested for the present series of ternary complexes. The plots of $\log K_{ML}^M$ or $\log K_{MAL}^{MAL}$ vs Z^2/r (not shown) are only slightly curved which may be due to partial covalent nature^{14,15} of the bond and varying degree of stabilization caused by the ligands.

The extra-stabilization energy (l.f.s.e) and 14Dq values for 1 : 1 LN-EDTA chelates from the stability constant data were calculated¹⁶ assuming them to be octahedral. This procedure has been used to calculate the 14Dq values for the 1 : 1 LN-EDTA chelates in the present study. The highest value of 14Dq corresponds to 140 cm⁻¹, indicating a small crystal field splitting. In lanthanides the ligand field causes the splitting of seven-fold degenerate f-level into three sub-levels, a_{2u}, t_{2u} and t_{1u}. It has been shown¹⁷ that the electron pairing energy in the a_{2u} sub-level is about 8000 cm⁻¹ which is much higher than the present maximum value of 14Dq. This suggests a 'high-spin' distribution of electrons in the LN-EDTA chelates.

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Determination of Stability Constants of N-(2-Hydroxy-1-naphthalidene)-benzylamine Complexes with Cu²⁺, Ni²⁺, Co²⁺ and Cd²⁺

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It is observed from the literature available that no work on the solution stability constants of N-(2-hydroxy-1-naphthalidene)-benzylamine and its metal complexes has been reported so far. The present investigation is aimed at determining the stability constants of the complexes of Cu²⁺, Ni²⁺, Cd²⁺ and Co²⁺ with N-(2-hydroxy-1-naphthalidene)-benzylamine.

Experimental

2-Hydroxy-1-naphthaldehyde (Fluka) was dissolved in ethanol (5 g, ~200 ml) and was cooled to 0°. To this solution, freshly distilled benzylamine slightly in excess of the equimolar quantity was added dropwise with constant stirring. The solution was allowed to stand for 2 h at room temperature. The reaction was monitored by tlc to confirm the absence of traces of aldehyde. The compound separated out on dilution. It was then repeatedly crystallised from alcohol-water mixture (50 : 50) to get analytically pure yellow coloured compound. Observed m.p. 96° (Found : C, 82.80 ; H, 5.79 ; N, 5.38. Calcd. for C₁₈H₁₅ON ; C 82.73, H, 5.74 ; N, 5.32%).

The Calvin-Bjerrum's pH titration technique as adapted by Irving and Rossotti¹ was used to determine the dissociation constant of the reagent and formation constants of its metal complexes at 30 ± 0.1° in 75 : 25 v/v dioxane-water. The Elico Model LI 15 pH meter was employed for pH determinations. During the titration oxygen free nitrogen presaturated with solvent mixture was bubbled through solution. The solutions of metal perchlorates were prepared using metal carbonates or oxides (A.R. grade). All these were standardised complexometrically by EDTA titrations².

The solutions titrated potentiometrically against standard carbonate free sodium hydroxide (1.08 M) solution were i) 5 ml (0.16 M) HClO₄ + 5 ml (0.64 M) NaClO₄ + 30 ml dioxane; (ii) 5 ml (0.16 M) HClO₄ + 5 ml (0.64 M) NaClO₄ + requisite amount of reagent accurately weighed to give 0.004 M reagent concentration in the final solution + 30 ml dioxane; and (iii) 5 ml (0.64 M) NaClO₄ + 5 ml metal perchlorate (0.008 M) in 0.16 M HClO₄ + the requisite amount of reagent accurately weighed to give 0.004 M reagent concentration in final solution + 30 ml dioxane. The titrations were performed in duplicate to test for reproducibility.